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Cross Pillar Activities Task 1: CESSDA Resource Directory

D2 Report on Resource Directory Activities in 2021

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Executive Summary

This document reports the main activities carried out in 2021 concerning the CESSDA Resource Directory (RD). The main activities included the elaboration of a policy and development strategy for the RD, the ongoing maintenance work, and the addition of new resources with a special focus on the inclusion of technical resources, such as tools and services used and/or developed by SPs around data archiving activities. These activities resulted in an increase of 186 resources (+78%) included in the RD for a total of 424 resources in December 2021.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CROSSDA	Croatian Social Science Data Archive
CSDA	Czech Social Science Data Archive
DAG	CESSDA Data Archiving Guide
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FORS	Swiss Center of Expertise in the Social Sciences
GESIS	Leibniz-Institute for the Social Sciences
MK DASS	Macedonian Social Science Data Archive
RD	CESSDA Resource Directory
SP	CESSDA Service Provider
SND	Swedish National Data Service
WG	CESSDA Working Group

Introduction

This report covers the 2021 activities regarding the CESSDA Resource Directory¹ (RD), a structured and documented collection of information on available documents, tools, and support services for data archive professionals. The work was divided into three subtasks: 1. Maintenance and regular updates of the CESSDA Resource Directory; 2. Contributions to the Resource Directory; and 3. Tools Directory. Specific activities within each subtask are presented in the following sections.

In 2021, the activities were carried out by FORS (as the lead partner), CROSSDA, CSDA, and SND. The work started after the end of the CESSDA Widening and Outreach Work Plan 2020, which also included activities related to the RD. A first information meeting inviting all partners (including GESIS and MK DASS that will be active in 2022) was organised on the 23rd of March to start the activities. Then, the team met once every two weeks until the end of the year, which allowed continuous cooperation, discussion and resolution of difficulties.

1. Maintenance and regular updates of the CESSDA Resource Directory

The activities performed in 2021 regarding this subtask were twofold. Firstly, the initial months were dedicated to the definition of the RD's policy and development strategy that will be published as a separate deliverable in 2022. This important document focuses on the governance and sustainability of the RD, the RD's collection development policy and curation process, as well as development strategies in terms of promotion and technical improvement.

Secondly, the team regularly maintained and updated the RD. In July, the 2021 new team members received training on the editorial work, based on the draft collection development policy and curation process defined in the first months of the project. Then, the whole team took part in the different maintenance and update activities, which consisted of reviewing the resources included in the RD and adding new resources.

The resources already included in the RD underwent three checks. The coherence of each resource with the collection development policy was first assessed. Inconsistent resources were deleted. Second, the resources placement in each category or subcategory was checked and, if needed, modified. Finally, the resources' links which are not persistent

¹ The CESSDA Resource Directory is available here: https://www.zotero.org/groups/2382601/cessda_resource_directory/library (15.12.2021).

identifiers (e.g., for web pages) were tested. Broken links were repaired when new web pages were found. Otherwise, resources had to be deleted.

Concerning adding new resources to the RD, the team first completed the curation of the resources shared by the SPs in 2020 (44 resources added) as well as the resources shared in the 2020 CESSDA newsletters (20 resources added). Second, the team included relevant resources shared in the 2021 CESSDA newsletters (7 resources added). Third, the team included all current CESSDA SPs Core Trust Seal certification reports (12). Moreover, the team used the certification to collect relevant resources (such as policies) and added them to the RD (70 resources added). Finally, to include new resources the team started also to follow the news shared in different Basecamp projects. Current team members are affiliated to the following eight Basecamps projects: CESSDA Service Providers' Directors, CESSDA Service Providers' Forum, CESSDA Metadata Office, CESSDA Training Group, CESSDA Trust Support, Dataverse for CESSDA, OAI-PMH endpoints, SSHOC.

An additional activity related to the RD was to review the explanatory text about the RD as well as the link provided in the CESSDA website.²

2. Contributions to the CESSDA Resource Directory

This sub-task is linked to the CESSDA Training Working Group (WG). The main goals were to support the usage of the content of the RD in the CESSDA Data Archiving Guide (DAG), to include resources created from the Training WG, and to create a user guide for the RD.

In 2021, the RD team and the DAG team met twice to discuss future collaborations. Indeed, the RD and the DAG have the same target audience, that is data archive professionals. Some collaborations are already agreed, e.g., including the DAG and all resources mentioned in the DAG in the RD, and other collaborations should be further discussed and tested in 2022. For example, the RD team could provide links to sets of topical resources that could be shared at the end of DAG chapters, in the sections "To go further/For more information". Since RD resources will be regularly checked for updates by the RD team, this could facilitate the maintenance of the DAG. It was also discussed that the DAG team should use the RD to find resources when developing new chapters and inform the RD team if no relevant resources were found. The RD team could then support the DAG team in looking for relevant resources that could also fill a gap in the RD. Finally, the collaborations could be further developed based on future technical improvements of the RD.

² CESSDA, Resource Directory: <https://www.cessda.eu/Tools-Services/For-Service-Providers/Resource-Directory> (15.12.2021).

No other training resources were included this year directly through collaboration with the Training WG. Collaboration with other teams Training WG should be strengthened next year. It should however be noted that most training resources developed target researchers who are not the RD's target audience.

Finally, the creation of the user guide was postponed to 2022.

3. Tools Directory

One main goal and activity of 2021 was to focus on the inclusion of technical tools and services resources developed and/or used by SPs for all activities connected to archiving data (e.g., anything from data acquisition to data dissemination, including also the management of users).

To do this, the team first identified relevant metadata for tools by examining metadata used in other projects gathering tools and considering needs specific to the RD. The resulting metadata scheme was used to prepare the collection tool that was sent to each CESSDA SP in June. A reminder was sent in September. Of the 23 SPs contacted, 16 SPs provided information, five were willing to send information later, two had nothing to report, and one did not answer.

In total, 93 resources about tools were collected from SPs. To select and review these resources a new and specific curation process for tools was developed and used. Moreover, to facilitate the discovery of these resources, specific subcategories were created (see Table 1, subcategories 4.1 to 4.6). A specific tag "Tools Directory"³ and topical tags were added to each tool included in the RD to offer an additional method for finding relevant resources.

In December 2021, 70 tools were described and tagged as "Tools Directory" in the RD. This decrease from 93 to 70 resources can be explained by:

- some resources shared by the SPs were not relevant for the RD;
- some resources were shared by multiple SPs;
- some resources were already present in the previous version of the RD; and finally
- some resources were not tools, but they were included as other types of resources if they were relevant for the RD.

³ Resources tagged as "Tools Directory" in the RD:
https://www.zotero.org/groups/2382601/cessda_resource_directory/collections/3WUX8IWK/tags/TOOLS%20DIRECTORY/collection (15.12.2021).

In total, category “4. Technical infrastructure” gathered 107 resources by December. It includes information about tools together with previously collected information about other technical resources.

4. Overview of the RD content

The resources have been organised under four main categories following the CoreTrustSeal requirements and the Open Archival Information System model:

- **Organisation** covers resources dealing with institutional management;
- **Digital object management** deals with activities around the acquisition, curation, dissemination and long-term preservation of data;
- **Communication and support to users** gathers resources on support, assistance and advice to users of the services;
- **Technical infrastructure** includes resources on hardware, software and tools needed to run the service, implementation and maintenance of technical systems and technical resilience.

Table 1 shows the distribution of resources by categories and subcategories at two time points, at the end of the RD 2020 project in March 2021 and in December 2021, at the middle of the RD 2021-2022 project. The 15th of December, the RD contained 424 resources. The number of resources increased by 78% since March 2021 and rose in almost all categories and subcategories. It should be noted that resources can be added in more than one category and subcategory. The high increase in resources between the end of 2020 project in March 2021 and December 2021 results mainly from the inclusion of tools resources and the addition of resources related to SPs’ Core Trust Seal certification.

Table 1: Comparison of the total number of resources and the number resources per category and subcategory between the end 2020 RD project and the 15th December 2021.

	RD 2021 project (December 2021)	RD 2020 project (March 2021)
Total	424 (+78%)	238
1. ORGANISATION	95 (+51%)	63
1.1 Organisational structure	40	28
1.2 Staffing, management and financing	8	10
1.3 National and international cooperation	12	10
1.4 Certification	40	27
1.5 Monitoring (new)	6	-
2. DIGITAL OBJECT MANAGEMENT	72 (+47%)	49
2.1 Pre-ingest - Acquisition	32	14
2.2 Ingest - Curation	36	17
2.3 Access - Dissemination	37	20
2.4 Preservation	28	15
3. COMMUNICATION AND SUPPORT TO USERS	178 (+59%)	112
3.1 General information about the institution	20	19
3.2 Data deposit	61	37
3.3 Data access	48	26
3.4 Data management	61	41
3.5 Data (re)use	34	17
4. TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	107 (+182%)	38
4.1. Pre-ingest - Acquisition (new)	10	-
4.2. Ingest - Curation (new)	31	-
4.3. Access - Dissemination (new)	42	-
4.4. Preservation (new)	17	-
4.5. Communication & user support (new)	16	-
4.6. Other (new)	26	-

Conclusion

Important work was accomplished in 2021 towards reaching the RD's goal of being a comprehensive and updated collection of important resources that help to build sustainable and mature data archives, to support the development of new services and features within existing data archives, and to inform data archive professionals about general data archiving practices and emerging topics.

In 2022, the activities concerning the RD will continue in this direction and pursue the goal of building a comprehensive and updated collection of important resources for data archive professionals. The team will first finalise the RD's policy and development strategy. Second, the maintenance and update of the collection will be done by contacting CESSDA WGs, SPs and partners. Third, the team will develop the user guide and start promoting the RD. Collaboration with the DAG team, as well as other teams in the Training WGs and in other WGs (e.g., the Mentorship team) will allow not only improving the content of the RD, but also presenting the RD to these teams. Moreover, the RD and DAG teams will consider promoting their tools together in 2022. Finally, the team will work towards the inclusion of the RD in the CESSDA website, which would provide the opportunity to improve some aspects of the RD (e.g., the search) and would also increase the visibility of the RD.